

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

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Guidance Notes

The purpose of this form is to support clear and comprehensive declaration of author interests in relation to journal submissions.

Our approach at EBT to the declaration and management of interests in relation to a submitted manuscript is different from most other scientific journals. Please read the following carefully.

- (1) An *interest* is any commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. For example, the interests that relate to running a lab, owning a company, being a shareholder, representing a charity, or being a PhD researcher will in many ways be different.
- (2) Interests may be financial or non-financial in nature.
- (3) A *conflict of interest* arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another interest. Note that having an interest is not the same thing as having a conflict of interest. For example, to be qualified for a job it is usually necessary to have an interest in the work.
- (4) Whether a conflict of interest exists is a fact about a relationship between interests, not an indicator of intent or state of mind, and does not in itself indicate any lapse in judgement or moral error. The presence of conflicts of interest is independent of the occurrence of inappropriate behavior.
- (5) Conflicts of interest matter because they have the potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in a research project - they put researchers in a position where they have to choose between their own interests and the interests of the project. Conflicts of interest therefore need to be identified and managed in order to preserve the integrity of decision-making when doing research.
- (6) The purpose of declaring interests is to provide editors, peer-reviewers, and readers of a manuscript the information they need to evaluate how effectively the authors said manuscript have managed their interests in relation to their research goals.
- (7) Contributors to a research project should declare all the interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that the interests that relate to the submitted work are known about, can be assessed for conflicts, and the conflicts then appropriately managed.
- (8) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.
- (9) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the author should state they are unable to complete the form.
- (10) The authors' approach to managing any identified conflicts of interest should be described in the methods or other appropriate section of their manuscript. If the declared interests are determined not to be in conflict, the authors should make this explicit and state that no measures were necessary for managing the declared interests. If there are conflicts of interest that the authors have not managed, this should be explained in the limitations section of the manuscript.

Author information

Name: Jan-Peter Nilsson

Date: Date

Title of manuscript: The Cognitive Exoskeleton: A Structured Pipeline for Augmented Intelligence in Scientific Formulation and Evidence Synthesis

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Corresponding Author

Interests

Please select "Yes" or "No" next to any interests below that are relevant to your situation

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by your submitted publication?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by your submitted publication?	
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input checked="" type="radio"/> No	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	<input checked="" type="radio"/> No	Publicly held positions or statements of public record
<input checked="" type="radio"/> No	From litigation or legal cases	<input checked="" type="radio"/> No	Personal relationships
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	From grants	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you may be seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
		<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have not received any monetary compensation for, or during, the production of this paper. However, I cannot exclude any possibilities that I will in the future receive economic

compensations from future work, derived directly from this publication, even if that is not the primary objective.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

If published, this production might have an impact on my standing, and lead to further involvement in groups interested in this specific subject. However, it is mainly written as a piece to contribute to the overall discussion on LLMs within scientific work. I wish to deliver a comment to balance the scale between AI alarmists, and the full on autonomy advocates.